

EXPRESSIVE SPEECH ACT OF BADMINTON LOVERS SLANG IN BADMINTON.INA INSTAGRAM A MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACH

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Abstract

Social media is a place where someone can express and communicate something widely. Through these media, various linguistic phenomena were found that can be used to create meaningful symbols, such as slang, as a stimulus in the interaction process. However, the impact of this phenomenon is not only positive but also harmful. For this reason, this study discusses the forms of slang in expressive speech acts and examines the function of Instagram post symbols uploaded by Badminton.Ina account. The method used is the descriptive-qualitative method. The results of this study found forms of expressive speech acts that function (1) insulting, (2) criticizing, (3) blaming, (4) insinuating, (5) encouraging, (6) praising, (7) hope, and (8) thanking. The function of expressive speech acts that often appears is the blame function because the posts uploaded by @badminton.ina in the Indonesian event are in decreased performance, making many comments appear more negative. Slang forms are found in the form of (1) Idioms, (2) Funny mispronunciations, (3) Word forms + suffixes, (4) Names/Nicknames, (5) Phrases, (5) Figurative and (6) Acronyms. The form of slang that often appears is the idiom form because BL, in creating slang, has more implied and indirect meanings. Then, the meaningful symbols used by @badminton.ina utilize Instagram upload features such as Photos, Highlights, Hashtags, Sponsors, Captions, Likes, and Comments. Based on the results, it can be understood that language phenomena can be interpreted from various perspectives. Sociopragmatics views slang as a form of language that impacts communication, while symbolic interactionism views slang as a verbal and nonverbal symbol that can support the interaction process in obtaining meaning.

Keywords: Speech Act, Slang, Symbolic Interactionism.

INTRODUCTION

The contemporary period that has led communication into mass media creates one's creativity in communicating, primarily through social media. In addition, since the pandemic to post-pandemic, direct communication has been more limited and requires users to be more active in communicating through the media. Although communication in situations is limited, communication will evolve like a living being capable of innovation [1]. The pandemic has changed communication habits in society by forming a new communication culture mediated by new media [2]. However, such conditions not only have a positive impact but also have a negative impact. Social changes caused by certain conditions and circumstances will have a positive and negative effects [3].

On the positive side, badminton fans spend time and energy watching their idols' matches. They have to go to the stadium, try to get tickets, and are willing to sit crowded to experience firsthand the atmosphere of a badminton match. However, technological developments have changed the way of enjoying badminton significantly. Now, badminton lovers are spoiled with easy access to online media. Through mobile phone screens, laptops, or even smart televisions, spectators can watch top badminton matches from different parts of the world as if they were in the

arena. This change in viewing patterns also has a significant impact and influence on fans and the development of badminton as a whole. Not only that, the pattern of change also affects the freedom to express matches and match results through language.

Language is a medium of interaction between people in the form of expressing themselves. It is usually said that language is expression, but expression when applied to language, cannot be understood as the simple, immediate, and naturally necessary manifestation of language [4]. The function of language is as a tool for self-expression. However, the form of expression itself is not only on the good side [5]. Language is a clear sign of both good and bad personalities. Thus, it can be said that through language, a person can express any feeling, be it happy, angry, or sad, to others in communication [6].

Instagram is a social media application based on someone who likes visuals and fun features to attract users' attention. Instagram is a forum often used by various groups [7]. Today's generation uses Instagram more than Facebook because its features are more exciting and complete [8]. Essentially, Instagram is a mobile-based application that enables users to take photos or pictures, apply different manipulation tools to transform the appearance of images and share them instantly with friends on other social networking sites [9]. In its use, this social media application is not only used as a place to express yourself through photos but also provides space to write comments in the photo upload. However, not all comments obtained are positive; they are also negative comments. In this case, the comments submitted by BL (Badminton Lovers) to Indonesian badminton athletes on the official Badminton Indonesia account @Badminton.Ina.

@badminton Ina's Instagram account is the official Instagram account of the Indonesia Association that Meta has verified with 1.7 million followers and 15.6 thousand posts. This account provides active information about the schedule and match results of all badminton events held by Indonesian athletes. They start withdrawing information and move on to the final match. The Indonesian badminton player sectors are Men singles, Women's Singles, men's Doubles, women's Double, and mixed double. Posts are presented in the form of photos and videos through instastory. The highest number of likes in the post was 150,000, with as many as 15,000 comments. This is because badminton is one of the sports in great demand several times in Indonesia compared to other sports. Every year, many achievements are made in the sport of badminton. Plus, one of the sectors, namely men's doubles, we are ranked first in the world, and the men's singles sector is ranked second in the world. We got eighth place in the women's singles sector, and women's doubles were sixth. It still did not get the top ten positions in the dual industry. This achievement is undoubtedly why badminton lovers visit and respond to the @Badminton.Ina account.

Unlike in 2023, the matches participated by Indonesian badminton athletes have ups and downs. Not many events can be won until the final and become the champion. Thus, BL always expresses comments of disappointment and criticism of badminton athletes because of the frequent decline in athletes' performance lately, especially throughout 2023. However, they also provide support and praise if they get good results. As stated in another account, @inabadminton.id, that badminton results throughout 2023 are indeed not optimal, as evidenced by only winning Malaysia masters R2, Singapore Open R1, Indonesia Open R2, Chinese Taipei Open R2,

Japan Open, R1, Australian Open R1, World Championship R3, China Open R1. The factors are technical, physical, nutritional, and mental, which are still very far from other countries such as China, Korea, and Japan. Thus, badminton lovers have expressed many negative comments towards @badminton.Ina posts. In addition, I found slang created by badminton lovers in the comments column. Slang is a language innovation in the form of a naturally occurring figure of speech used by adolescents and scholars to indicate distinctiveness in language, but not long-lived. Slang is a less standard and seasonal language a specific group requests [10].

In the previous research, Margiyanti & Andik [11] examined slang in the Instagram account @Moodrekeh.ID, which describes slang's form, meaning, and function. The findings of this study are intended to compare standard and non-standard languages in the language learning process. Caption @lambeturah_official's Instagram account found 21 forms of expressive speech acts. Usman & Hasriani [12] examined the variety of slang in the language of Makassar Instagram celebrity advertisements: A Pragmatic Guide that finds forms of deixis, presuppositions, and implications in the use of slang. Jamila et al. [13] examined the Analysis of Symbolic Interactionism on Purepurpose Photography Instagram Posts. This research explained that Purepurpose uses the POAC concept in building company management, and the photos have the characteristics of symbols that have meaning. Then, research by Khasanah & Nunik [14], Analysis of Expressive Speech Acts on Instagram Account Captions @Arief22_Rahmansholeh, found four forms of expressive speech acts: expressive longing, worry, congratulations, and appreciation. These findings are expected to contribute to building polite language when communicating, especially on social media. Yasa and Santika [15] examined the types of code mixing found in Badminton fans' tweets. Research findings indicate that Twitter users use three forms of code mix: insertion, replacement, and congruent lexicalization.

Based on some of the studies above, the differences with previous studies are (1) comments in the Instagram column @Badminton_Ina were not only absolute in the form of BL expressions to badminton athletes, but the use of slang in the speech was found. (2) Also, BL comes from various circles and not only among teenagers, although slang is more often found among teenagers. (3) Badminton is one of the most requested sports compared to other sports (4) Analysis is also seen from the point of view of symbolic interactionism in @Badminton_Ina posts as a form of individual role in interacting on social media. Symbolic interactionism is the actions and interactions that stem from a process by which an object can be interpreted or interpreted. There are three principles in symbolic interactionism: meaning, language, and thought [16].

This research was conducted during the BWF World Champion event at the Denmark Open on 23 August to 8 September 2023, which was held in Denmark & Shoungzhou. They started with the initial round of R32 and continued to the final round. The matches at this event were attended by various countries, both Asian and European. At the BWF World Champion, Denmark hosted, and the China Open hosted directly. Then, the Denmark open event took place at the Jyske Bank Arena, Odense, and Denmark immediately hosted.

Based on the description above, the problems discussed in this study are (1) What are the forms of expressive speech in the BL comment column on Badminton Indonesia Instagram (2) Slang forms in the BL comment column on Instagram @Badminton.Ina? (3) Then, the meaning and symbolic function of the post @badminton.Ina. This study

aims to describe expressive speech forms, slang forms in the BL comment column on Instagram @Badminton.Ina, and symbolic meanings in @Badminton.Ina posts.

The theoretical basis used in this study is sociopragmatic studies, which include pragmatic and sociolinguistic studies. Then, the theory of communication is symbolic interactionism. In pragmatic studies, there are studies of speech acts, and in sociolinguistics, there is a study of language variation as a social phenomenon, such as slang. Then, the theory of communication, namely symbolic interactionism, views language as interpreted based on symbols.

Austin, in his book "How to Do Things with Words," states that speech act is all speech is performative in that all speech is a form of action and not just speech [17]. Searle said that communication is not just symbols, words, or sentences but the result of all three in speech act behavior. Searle distinguishes the forms of speech acts into 5, namely (1) Representatives, namely actions that speakers trust in an event; (2) Directives, namely actions that have an impact on speech partners; (3) Exspresives, which are related to what is felt by the speaker, (4) Asertives, which are words spoken are actions for the future and (5) Declarations, namely words to express something. Thus, it can be interpreted as an act of speech to express a certain attitude. Context is needed to understand the speech act [18, 19].

Leech mentions that context is a matter of knowledge of the physical and social worlds. As well as sociological factors affecting communication [20]. Furthermore, Cutting divides context into three types, namely situational, cultural, and interpersonal background [21]. Then, according to Depraetere, context plays an important role in pragmatic studies because the speech produced is not only a matter of meaning but meaning based on situational or situational conditions of speakers and interlocutors [22]. Thus, it can be understood that context is the basis for interpreting a speech in pragmatic studies.

Slang forms into 4 are (1) abbreviation, which is one of the shortening in the form of letters or a combination of letters; (2) funny mispronunciation, which is a modification of pitch height or a unique statement as a form of expression of taste, (3) shortened forms, namely short forms found in various languages, (4) Interjection, which is a form that cannot be affixed or syntactic support [23]. Then, the slang form, namely (1) figurative, which is a group of words that have a certain effect; (2) Nicknames, which are unofficial and not following the original name; (3) Word idioms that are interpreted indirectly, (4) Phrases and Sentences, which are language units in the form of phrases or clauses [24].

The theory of symbolic interactionism is a way of viewing and thinking of someone in communicating to mean something within a certain period and intended for specific actions. Interactionism describes language, social interaction, and reflectivity. There are three crucial concepts in symbolic interactionism: (1) Mind is a process of individuals interacting with themselves using meaningful symbols that produce stimulus; It is through symbols that thoughts can be formed. (2) Self, which is self-reflection that can adjust the conditions, meanings, and effects of the process of interaction or the perspective of others. By the sense of the word, not only receive but produce a stimulus in action. (3) Society is the relationship between action patterns and interaction in community life using symbols, which are then understood through the learning process [25].

METHOD

This study used a qualitative descriptive method. Qualitative descriptive research describes and describes data as it is from a phenomenon or event without any manipulation process or other treatments [26]. The purpose is to expose and describe an event. This study describes the form of excretive speech acts, slang, and symbols in the @Badminton.Ina Instagram account. The source of data obtained is in the form of components presented in posts in the form of photos/images through Instagram features and words contained in the comment column. The technique used is to observe and document the posting of the results of @badminton matches. Ina. Then, the data obtained are classified. Thus, the data obtained were analyzed based on expressive speech acts, slang forms, and symbolic interactionism analysis.

DISCUSSION

a) Slang Analysis in Expressive Illocutionary Speech Acts

Illocutionary speech acts are acts that do not only function to say what the speaker speaks but can also be used to do something. Speech acts like this usually have a specific function and purpose. Then, an express speech act is a speech act that means what is conveyed is an evaluation of what is communicated and reveals the psychological attitude of the speaker toward a situation. Usually, it is in the form of positive expressions such as saying thank you, congratulations, apologizing, praising, condolences, flattering, and encouraging. Negative things are also expressed as insulting, accusing, criticizing, berating, blaming, insinuating, and cornering. The findings of BL's expressive speech act findings in the Instagram comment column of Badminton.ina's post are as follows;

Forms of expressive speech acts of badminton lovers

Based on the findings above, the most dominant form of speech act is insulting speech act. That's because fans have high expectations of badminton athletes, so that every defeat will be a very disappointing event. Then, BL created communication on badminton.ina Instagram account also creates various forms of slang as follows;

Slang forms in expressive speech acts of badminton lovers

The uniqueness of badminton lovers in expressing their speech and commenting on each match creates slang forms in communicating. The form that often appears is the form of idioms. This is because badminton lovers predominantly come from teenagers, so the potential slang that occurs more often in idioms is to show creativity, interest, and short.

The speech data analysis is as follows;

@Badminton.lna's post in the BWF Championship 2023 event.

Data (1)

Context: The post contains information that one of the sectors, namely MD, currently ranked 1st in the World, namely Fajar Alfian & M. Rian, lost in R32. Fajar/Rian lost to unseeded Chinese Taipei athletes Lee Jhe-Huei & Yang Po-Hsuan. @youdrhope:" Ya. Elah Turu!"

The above remarks are an insulting expressive speech act. The word "Turu" means burden/troublesome/undeveloped. The speaker expressed his frustration and dissatisfaction with the results given to Indonesian badminton athletes because they had to lose in the early rounds. Speakers not only write comments as a form of expression but also insult the Rank 1 athlete who only relies on titles but playing is not optimal.

The word "Turu" comes from Javanese, which means sleep. But the word "Turu" in this context implies burden, trouble, or not growing. The word is categorized as idiom slang because the meaning of the word has a new meaning that represents a particular expression.

Data (2)

Context: The post contains information that one sector, WS Putri KW, lost to world No. 2 Akane Yamaguchi in two sets. Every KW women's match still hasn't reached the final since 2022.

@borieellll: "Setelan Pabrik"

The above remarks are an insulting expressive speech act. The phrase "Factory Settings" means standard settings. Speakers expressed frustration that the KW Women's athletes have not given their best results in every tournament throughout

2022-2023. The current condition of WS also has full expectations for Gregoria and Princess. However, Putri has not given her best like Grego.

In this context, the phrase "Factory Settings" means ordinary/ standard/ undeveloped. Based on its meaning, the phrase is categorized into nickname slang because it is often used by BL when commenting on KW Women's athletes.

@Badminton.Ina's post in the BWF Championship 2023 event.

Data (3)

@Ridagsnt: "Bapuk"

The above speech is an expressive speech act of criticizing. The word "Bapuk" means ugly/old man. The speaker presented his argument about the Fajar/Rian athlete's game, which was not optimal, and he looked confused on the court. The athlete's game is considered imperfect/flawed when measured by the ranking owned by Fajar / Rian.

The word "Bapuk" comes from the Malay word old man. But in this context, the meaning of the word "Bapuk" is ugly/bad. This word is included in slang and is usually more often found in the comments column on @badminton.Ina's Instagram account. The word is categorized as slang.

Data (4) @Badminton.Ina's post in the BWF Championship 2023 event.

@matchaa_kakes "Mangsed"

The above remarks are expressive acts of blame. The word "Mangsed" means disappointed/sad. The speaker expressed his disappointment because he had expected Indonesia to be happy but lost mentally and finally lost even though the score was far ahead. The word "Mangsed" comes from two combinations of the phrase "emang pathetic." This word is categorized into slang because BL circles often use it. The form of the word is categorized into acronym slang because it combines two abbreviated syllables shorter and does not create new meanings.

Data (4)

@dhnywahnyunii: "Gokil"

Context: The post contains information that one of the WD sectors, namely Apriyani & Fadia, is the only Indonesian representative who advanced in the final party in the BWF World Champion event. They faced WD athletes ranked one, Chen & Jia Yifan. Despite being runners-up, they were highly appreciated by BL for being able to bring achievements to the finals and become the only representatives.

The above speech is an express act of praise. "gokil" comes from the word "crazy," which means exciting, engaging, and funny. The speaker appreciated and expressed his admiration for Apriyani and Fadia for fighting to climb the podium on behalf of all other Indonesian athletes. This is supported by the condition that achieving the runner-up position is not easy because other colleagues have lost a lot and failed at the beginning of the Round. The word "Gokil" belongs to the slang form of idioms because the word has a new meaning representing a particular expression.

@Badminton.Ina's post in the China Open 2023 event.

Data (5)

@Yuhanerie: "Di Luar Nurul"

Context: The post contains information that one of the sectors, namely MD, which is currently ranked 1st in the World, namely Fajar Alfian & M. Rian, lost in R32. Fajar/Rian lost to Danish No. 8 seeds Kim Astrup & Anders in two sets. After losing at the BWF event, now China Open, they also suffered a defeat in the early rounds.

The above speech is a satirical expressive speech act. Speech Outside Nurul comes from words outside reason, which means it is not according to expectations or is not based on reason. Speakers satirized the athlete Fajar/Rian, who lost again in R32 at the China Open. This is supported by the condition that athletes ranked 1st in the world often experience defeat. After losing the previous tournament in R32 and subsequent tournaments also losing to R32, speakers assumed they were playing inappropriately to their current position.

The phrase "Outside Nurul" is widely used on social media, especially by BL. The sentence means a result that does not follow expectations. The sentence is also categorized into a funny mispronunciation slang.

b) Analysis of symbolic interactionalism of Badminton.Ina's Instagram posts

The posts are the results of matches during the 2023 BWF World Champion, China Open, and Denmark Open.

@Badminton.Ina is a forum for distributing information about Indonesian athletes' activities, especially in badminton. Through its presentation, match information becomes an update. In addition, the presentation component continues to be consistent, always built with several essential components to convey information. The presentation of the post includes;

Photograph

It is a natural form of information related to badminton athletes' matches. The photos presented are scenes that took place during the game. This is so that badminton lovers can see athletes in real life even though they cannot watch live matches broadcast. Both in terms of conditions on the field and the costumes used by athletes. In addition, the photo is equipped with badminton.ina logo, which has always been a mainstay image for showing copyright. Through photos, badminton.ina implicitly not only conveys concrete information related to match results but also shows the struggle of athletes in the match. This is supported by photos being always displayed in top condition and fighting in a game. Whether you lose or win, the consistency of uploading photos of athletes remains the same. This means that photos are not only a symbol of supporting information but also a form of interaction between athletes' efforts and hard work in a match and badminton lovers.

Highlight

The score number is the primary information related to the match. To convey information to badminton lovers, consistently winning and losing scores will be highlighted. In its posts, Badminton.ina always uses white-in score uploads to show neutrality. In addition to the score highlights, the post also displays the names of athletes who competed with complete BWF rankings as well as flags. This ranking is also a highlight of the achievements of athletes competing to support the results of match information. Then, the highlight in the post is the tenure event that is being followed. It aims to convey the results of matches in AMSA events participated by athletes.

Hashtags

Badminton.ina uses hashtags in its posts following ongoing events. It aims to make it easier for the information conveyed to be accessible to anyone who is looking for related events. This means that the reach of posts that can be accessed will be more expansive when searches are carried out using match event keywords. In addition, hashtags are also used to categorize and match information from each event that is also equipped with the year. The goal is that different events are not in the exact search because, generally, badminton matches every year will be the same. For that, it needs to be distinguished by using the keyword year.

Sponsored

Sponsorship is a symbol of effective communication used to build engagement in an event, company, or community. Indonesian badminton athletes are sponsored by three major companies: Bank Negara Indonesia, Kapal Api, and Scarlet. Based on these three sponsors, BNI has been the main sponsor since 2021. The addition of a sponsor icon to the post shows an appreciation to those who have financially supported badminton athletes and also participated in promoting sponsors to the community, especially badminton lovers.

Caption

It serves as a symbol of conveying a message in writing. In addition, captions can complement image/photo information posted through the Instagram homepage. Badminton.lna posted a caption of the match results delivered in straightforward language and added words of support for both losing and winning. Like the words "keep the spirit" if the result of the game is lost and when winning like "What a game," "Well done," "Thank You," or "Great game."

Like & Comment

It serves as a non-verbal symbol that can indicate the response to the process of communication. The like and comment feature allows the public, especially badminton lovers, to respond in the form of a love icon and write comments on posts. However, the presence of the love icon as a symbol does not necessarily show a positive support response; it also indicates a negative response. Unlike the comment column, which can clearly express words as a form of expressing a reaction to the result of the match.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research and discussion results, the construction of communication through social media can lead to the emergence of various phenomena and create different impacts. Such is the emergence of creative forms of language to express something. However, development is not always considered positive; it is also harmful, like slang formed from the process of creativity in language. From a linguistic point of view, especially sociopragmatic, slang is seen as a variety of languages that cannot be understood only by many people and some groups and communities. In addition, slang is constantly evolving and not fixed. As a result, language users freely form meanings that lead to positive and negative things. Then, slang has an impact on language development and threatens the structure of language. The reason is that the development of new forms of language may reduce one's awareness of good and correct language. In contrast to the perspective of symbolic interactionism communication studies, the phenomenon and creativity of language, both verbally and non-verbally, become an interaction process to obtain a response. All forms of response, positive or negative, result from the stimulus that has been built. In other words, if creativity in language, such as slang and the use of social media features, is present in communication, it becomes an agreed symbol to create an understanding of its users.

Research related to expressive speech acts has been done before. Broadly speaking, research only shows the forms and meanings of expressive speech acts. However, this study shows the presence of slang as a form of expressive speech acts that innovate. Through slang, expressive speech acts can show the differentiator of the badminton fan community in communicating with other communities.

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